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& IQTISODIYOT

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ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

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- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
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- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
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- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
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- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR ENSURING FOOD SECURITY AND ITS STRUCTURAL COMPOSITION

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Abstract: This article discusses the socio-economic necessity, existing opportunities, priority areas, organizational and economic mechanism and its structural structure of ensuring food security.

Key words: food, food security, mechanism, organizational and economic mechanism, structure.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy zaruriyati, mavjud imkoniyatlari, ustuvor yo'nalishlari, tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi va uning tarkibiy tuzilishi yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oziq-ovqat, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, mexanizm, tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizm, tuzilish.

Аннотация: В данной статье выделены социально-экономическая необходимость, существующие возможности, приоритеты, организационно-экономический механизм и его структурная структура обеспечения пищевой безопасности.

Ключевые слова: продовольствие, безопасность пищевых продуктов, механизм, организационно-экономический механизм, структура.

INTRODUCTION

Food security is one of the most fundamental conditions for sustainable socio-economic development, public health, social stability and national security. In the modern global economy, ensuring food security is no longer limited only to increasing agricultural production. It requires a complex system of organizational, economic, institutional, technological and social measures aimed at guaranteeing the availability, accessibility, quality and stability of food supplies for the population.

Therefore, the development of an effective organizational and economic mechanism for ensuring food security has become an important scientific and practical issue. The organizational and economic mechanism for ensuring food security represents a system of interrelated institutions, methods, instruments and regulatory measures through which the state, business entities, agricultural producers, logistics organizations, financial institutions and consumers interact in the food system. This mechanism includes state regulation, market incentives, financial support, infrastructure development, investment attraction, price stabilization, food reserve management, quality control, innovation implementation and risk management. Its main purpose is to create favorable conditions for the stable production, processing, distribution and consumption of safe and sufficient food products.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

It is known that the concept of "mechanism" originally emerged in technological sciences and is interpreted as a device designed to transform and transmit motion. An organizational and economic mechanism is a method of substantiating and achieving goals, forming and developing a management system, and organizing the production process [1]. The improvement of a specific type of mechanism is carried out with due consideration of a particular objective [2]. The rationality of the organizational mechanism consists of the following components: rules, organizational and legal regulations, standards, the distribution of tasks among different executors, management, and others [3].

Therefore, the organizational mechanism, in turn, is also expressed through economic relations. Having

studied research works aimed at analyzing the structural composition of the organizational and economic mechanism, it can be concluded that it serves as a structural element of a higher-level economic mechanism. However, a number of researchers put forward opposing views, arguing that these are equivalent concepts and that the concept of the economic mechanism has gradually transformed over time into the concept of the organizational and economic mechanism [4].

The essence of the organizational and economic mechanism consists in the rational interaction of forms of organizing activities, which are directly determined by the type and form of the object. In other words, within the framework of the organizational and economic mechanism, it is necessary to take into account both the objectives of activity and its organizational forms.

In research studies, primary attention is paid to the adaptive characteristics of the organizational and economic mechanism. However, insufficient attention is given to the elements that ensure the self-development of individual sectors. In particular, the need to preserve crop rotation systems, fertilization systems, production organization systems, and labor organization systems is directly related to the adaptive characteristics of the organizational and economic mechanism.

Furthermore, the transition from the effective organization of technological processes to the organization of business processes automatically contributes to ensuring economic sustainability. However, in this case, environmental and social sustainability must not be weakened. This is because the irrational use of land and labor resources may lead to the destruction of the entire system [5]. The above indicates the interrelationship of methods and forms of organizational and economic influence aimed at stimulating the effective activities of entities involved in ensuring food security.

At the same time, the organizational and economic mechanism represents a set of organizational structures, specific forms and methods of management, economic laws operating under particular conditions, and the forms through which the reproduction process is carried out [6].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study is based on the collection of data from scientific literature, theoretical sources, and analytical studies related to food security and organizational-economic mechanisms. Comparative, logical, and systematic analysis methods were applied to evaluate existing approaches, identify structural elements of the mechanism, and analyze the interrelationships between organizational, economic, ecological, and management factors in ensuring food security

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

By summarizing the studies aimed at revealing the content and essence of such concepts as “mechanism”, “economic mechanism” and “organizational mechanism”, it can be concluded that the organizational and economic mechanism includes the following provisions: the organizational and economic mechanism is a link in the management system that helps bring the object into an operational state and ensure its stable functioning; the lower-level elements constituting the organizational and economic mechanism may be represented in the form of planning, financing, personnel management and support, resource allocation, control and other sets of measures; the organizational and economic mechanism is determined at the national, regional, urban, local and organizational levels. The organizational and economic mechanism is recommended by taking into account the need to influence the object and to create sufficient conditions for the behavior of subjects and management objects (Figure 1).

Figure 1. General Structure of the Organizational and Economic Mechanism¹ [7]

Thus, the main structural components of the organizational and economic mechanism, firstly, possess a structural characteristic that reflects the force of influence, and secondly, they are in constant motion or are distinguished by their functionality.

The organizational and economic mechanism reflects the processes of creation, formation, distribution, or utilization. This is because forms or elements cannot interact with one another by themselves. The implementation of this process or interaction is directly related to the functions of the organizational and economic mechanism [8]. The main feature of the organizational and economic mechanism is that it reflects specificity or is oriented toward achieving clearly defined goals and fulfilling specific tasks. It also serves as a means of achieving objectives and solving problems [9]. The organizational and economic mechanism implies achieving specific goals and objectives through a system of interrelated ecological, technical, technological and economic instruments, a set of organizational, administrative and socio-psychological methods, as well as systems of motivation and responsibility [10].

In the field of ensuring food security, the organizational and economic mechanism of management simultaneously requires taking natural factors into account and being adaptable to them. These natural factors are determined by the following:

- taking into account the specific characteristics of production units under different soil and climatic conditions;

¹ Source: developed by the author.

- the need to redistribute natural and production resources;
- the flexibility of using economic instruments in the process of making managerial decisions, and others.

The above should include a combination of forms, principles, methods and instruments aimed at implementing strategies and objectives related to ensuring food security, as well as fully satisfying all forms and types of interests of the participants involved in this field.

In general, the organizational and economic mechanism of management is a synergy of interrelated structural components. This determines the economic, organizational and socio-psychological methods of management applied at different hierarchical levels of governance in order to implement objectives, functions and principles (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Organizational and Economic Mechanism of Management² [11]

According to these views, the organizational and economic mechanism is a synergy of organizational and economic mechanisms, which, in turn, consist of organizational and economic methods, instruments, and means of influencing the object of management. The analysis shows that the organizational and economic mechanism can be defined by two complementary levels: the market mechanism of self-organization at all levels and the system of state regulation.

The main criteria for the effective functioning of the organizational and economic mechanism are as follows: self-protection and self-management of any object; adaptation to changing market conditions; and the establishment of a balance between object management and adaptation to market conditions[12].

2 Source: developed by the author.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the above analysis, it should be concluded that, in improving the organizational and economic mechanism for ensuring food security, it is necessary to take into account the interrelation between the development characteristics of agriculture and the processing industry and natural processes. Therefore, the organizational and economic mechanism for ensuring food security represents the influence of methods aimed at maintaining interconnections within the system of “nature – production – ecology.”

The effective functioning of this mechanism requires the coordinated interaction of state institutions, agricultural producers, processing enterprises, market infrastructure and consumers. In this regard, special attention should be paid to the improvement of economic incentives, resource allocation, monitoring systems and institutional support aimed at strengthening food security. The integration of organizational, economic, ecological and technological instruments makes it possible to increase the stability, adaptability and efficiency of the food supply system. Thus, improving the organizational and economic mechanism for ensuring food security is an important factor in achieving sustainable agricultural development, protecting consumer interests and strengthening national economic resilience.

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